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^{99m}Tc-MIBI SCINTIGRAPHY MULTIPLE MYELOMA: COMPARATION WITH X-RAY SKELETAL SURVEY

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Background and objectives: In multiple myeloma, imaging is required to determine the stage of disease and to anticipate impending bone fractures. Technetium-99m 2-methoxyisobutylisonitrile (^{99m}Tc-MIBI) has been proposed as a useful tracer for the detection of disease sites in patients with multiple myeloma (MM). The goal of this study was to determine the potential role of ^{99m}Tc-MIBI imaging for the evaluation of the extent of primary disease in comparison with X-ray skeletal survey.

Method: Thirty eight patients with multiple myeloma were studied using ^{99m}Tc-MIBI. Of the 38 patients included in this study, 14 were in stage I, 13 in stage II and 11 in stage III. Anterior and posterior whole-body imaging were obtained 10 min after I.V. injection of 370 MBq of ^{99m}Tc-MIBI. Four different MIBI pattern could be described in our patients: physiological (P), diffuse (D), focal (F) and combined diffuse and focal (D+F).

Results: In comparison to conventional x-ray skeletal survey, ^{99m}Tc-MIBI scans showed a higher number of myeloma bone disease at diagnosis. All patients with stage II and III multiple myeloma were positive with ^{99m}Tc-MIBI scans at diagnosis. The pattern of positive MIBI accumulation were diffuse in 31 (82%) patients, focal in 2 (5%) and combined focal and diffuse in 5 (13%) patients. The intensity of ^{99m}Tc-MIBI correlated with stage of diseases.

Conclusion: ^{99m}Tc-MIBI scintigraphy is a reliable method to evaluate bone marrow activity in patients with multiple myeloma.

